

EGI Contribution to the EOSC Federation

Discussion paper

V.1.2 07-05-2024

Abstract

Compute, storage, research objects, services and analytics tools are integral to the Open Science Commons and the realisation of the EOSC vision. This paper describes how EGI Federation envisages their provision as a collaborative effort of Research Infrastructures and e-Infrastructures, to jointly provide compute and co-located data services for international, grand challenge applications under the EOSC Node architecture.

This discussion paper reflects the EGI Federation's current thinking on collaborative service provision within the EOSC framework. We believe a strong, collaborative approach is essential for the success of EOSC. We welcome your feedback and insights, which will inform the further development of this position.

Introduction

A collaborative approach is the hallmark of modern science and research. Scientists and researchers, from different disciplines and countries, work together to advance humanity's understanding of the world around us. As science and research become more “digital” – combining both digital assets and digital tools and services to increase the speed and excellence of scientific process – those digital assets and services must also be used collaboratively and increasingly provided and shared on a collaborative basis. Several terms have been used to describe this collaborative process, including open science commons and research ecosystems. Both terms point to concepts from economics.

There is great potential in investigating how this can be better applied to the interrelated resource systems that are needed to support the open creation and dissemination of scholarly knowledge.

In 2015, EGI presented a vision for an Open Science Commons (OSC)¹ as an approach for sharing and governing advanced digital services, scientific instruments, data, knowledge and expertise that enables European researchers to collaborate more easily, be more productive and achieve higher levels of excellence.

The Open Science Commons builds on the understanding that managing shared resources as a Commons maximises excellence in science and benefits society. Applying this principle to the Open Science process is expected to (1) democratise access to research objects otherwise difficult or impossible to access, and (2) create clear and non-discriminatory access rules together with the sense of shared ownership that stimulates a higher level of participation, cooperation and social reciprocity.

When applied in Open Science in Europe, the principles of the Commons imply that :

- Sharing is applied to research data, scientific instrumentation, digital services, software, publications, education and training and expertise.
- Access models are well-defined and non-discriminatory for all entities participating in the Commons.
- Harmonised access policies are available, offering clear points of access and support.
- Services are managed transparently, maintaining service access and quality while spanning multiple organisations as providers.
- Governance is participatory.
- Long-term support of funding agencies allows for infrastructures to take a long-term view and build for a common European future.

¹ 'Open Science Commons', S. Andreozzi et al., <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4884748> and <https://www.egi.eu/publication/open-science-commons-vision/>

The Research Data Alliance (RDA) formed an interest group to better understand the concept of *Global Open Research Commons* (GORC) as ‘a global trusted ecosystem that provides seamless access to high-quality interoperable research outputs and services’². The resulting GORC model identified the following components as essential elements of the Commons (Figure 1), some of which are the assets to be accessed by researchers, and some are supporting components:

- Compute, Storage, Network, AAI
- Research objects
- Services and Tools
- Interoperability and standards
- Human Capacity
- Rules of Participation and Access
- Governance Structures
- Engagement and Sustainability.

Figure 1. The ‘Compute, Storage Network and AAI’ component in the context of the RDA Global Open Research Commons reference model.

² Payne, K., Corrie, B., Crawley, F., Harrower, N., Macneil, R., Maxwell, L., Sansone, S.-A., Treloar, A., Woodford, C., Åkerström, W. N., & RDA GORC International Model WG. (2023). The Global Open Research Commons International Model Report, Version 1 (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00097>

The EOSC contribution to the Open Research Commons

EGI recognises the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) as the European initiative to support the implementation of the Global Open Research Commons across Europe, leveraging the capabilities of Research Infrastructures, e-Infrastructures, and other EOSC stakeholders at national, regional and European level.

Of the essential elements of the Commons, the RDA GORC report suggests ten different capabilities to be delivered under the 'services and tools' category, some of which address the needs of specific research disciplines, while others are of a general purpose nature. In alignment with the RDA GORC approach, we suggest the EOSC value proposition should include:

Specialised capabilities

- Research object repositories
- Services and tools for direct research tasks
- Vocabulary and semantic object services

General purpose capabilities

- Commons catalogue of all services and tools
- Discovery service
- Services and tools that enable workflows and middleware
- Persistent identifier services
- Data management services and tools
- Security and identification services
- Helpdesk service

The EOSC Federation model needs to define the governance according to which its members contribute to the delivery of these important Commons capabilities listed above. The provisioning of some of these will be coordinated and aligned by the EOSC Federation (single or distributed depending on the governance of choice), while the provisioning of others will be devolved to the EOSC Federation members.

EGI as EOSC Node

EGI Federation has provided many of the essential elements identified by GORC. The mission of the EGI Federation is to continue to do so; aligning its vision with other e-Infrastructures, Research Infrastructures and EOSC is an important task to ensure synergies and leverage of expertise.

The Role of Computing in EOSC

Computing and Storage is one of the GORC model components as shown in Figure 1. As a Commons component, these services are delivered in conjunction with technical support and co-design, directly accessed by researchers or indirectly accessed by data analytics tools in the 'Services and Tools' category. As noted by the RDA GORC report, 'research infrastructure, services and tools are often made available through research platforms (variously referred to as virtual science labs, virtual research environments (VREs), or Science Gateways) that are deployed to support both the research workflows and the communities of practice engaged in collaborative research'.

Compute and Storage are the capabilities by which value is added to existing research data through its re-use and combination with other data – by researchers from any discipline and any country.

The EGI infrastructure federates research data centres, co-locating compute capacity and research data holdings as a distributed system, and leveraging IT infrastructure procured by research-performing organisations and member states. As such, EGI is positioned to become a European multi-site EOSC Node.

The EGI Federation aspires to be part of the EOSC Federation as a Node contributing EOSC-dedicated capacity, available for transnational access to services operated within the other EOSC Nodes (Services and Tools, Research Objects – ROs), and to international use cases directly served by the EGI EOSC Node. The capacity dedicated to the EGI EOSC Node would be contributed from selected compute-data centres of the EGI federation.

We envisage the EGI node capabilities to be accessed by EOSC users either directly, in a *B2C* fashion, or indirectly, in a *B2B* fashion, as integrated components of research infrastructures.

Integration scenarios with EOSC EU Node

EGI EOSC Node compute capabilities can integrate with the EOSC EU Node according to two scenarios:

- **Scenario 1.** Extend the compute and storage capacity and time allocations offered by the EOSC EU Node, with capacity and research data hosted by the EGI Federated Cloud providers and partnering Research Infrastructures (<https://www.egi.eu/egi-infrastructure/>). In this scenario the EOSC EU Node is the business channel towards users. This integration would allow the EOSC EU Node to serve a wider set of research communities and to satisfy more demanding requirements. The Application Workflow Management (AWM) component of the EOSC

EU Node can serve as an integration point allowing it to identify and automatically redirect workloads to the integrated cloud providers according to user parameters such as required compute capacity and data physical location, and information from the EOSC Resource Catalogue.

- **Scenario 2.** Aggregate user demand from EGI research communities and projects (e.g. communities of practice, long tail of science and Research Infrastructures) and act as a user proxy towards the EOSC EU Node services, for example to enable co-located processing and analysis of research data hosted by the EOSC EU Node, and to integrate it with advanced computing, datasets, models, software and user support provided by the EGI Federation. In this scenario EGI provides the business channel towards the user communities. This integration would create an additional delivery channel for the EOSC EU Node that would lead to an increased utilisation. AWM recipes can be made accessible to the EGI user base and served by the EOSC EU Node, as target infrastructure, in conjunction with the EGI infrastructure. Furthermore, EGI can contribute advanced recipes to be registered in the EOSC EU Node AWM and made available to all the EOSC EU Node users.

In both Scenario 1 and Scenario 2 research communities will be able to access data and infrastructure from two or more EOSC nodes as one integrated offer.

EGI Contribution to the EOSC Core

Nowadays, EGI is involved in both the delivery of the EOSC EU Node and in the development of the next generation of EOSC Core services, including the piloting of the EOSC Node concept, with the EOSC Beyond project starting in April 2024.

As part of the EOSC Beyond project, EGI is committed to contributing with the project partners to the evolution of the current EOSC Core concept introducing new Core services that advance Open Science and innovation in research, allowing scientific applications to integrate, compose and use multiple EOSC Resources (datasets, services, etc) from national, regional and thematic EOSC Nodes. EGI will participate in the delivery of the new generation of the EOSC Core services establishing an EOSC Node that integrates its distributed computing infrastructure and its advanced services for data access, use and re-use in EOSC for exploitation by European researchers.

Democratisation of AI for research

The discovery of new knowledge increasingly relies on the availability of AI-ready data and models to be trained on research data from multiple sources. Efficient access to distributed high quality data, computing capacity, AI tools and technical support for distributed model training, fine-tuning and model serving, is critical to support the research process. Researchers are confronted by the lack of transnational access to and scarcity of

computational resources to host machine-learning models (on the cloud or on premises) and to make their functions available via API so that applications can incorporate AI into their systems. Model serving is particularly crucial, as research excellence increasingly depends on the availability of AI products to a large user base, AI-ready data and technical support [³].^[4],^[5].

AI democratisation puts AI into the hands of European researchers without specialised AI and technical knowledge, empowering them with open-source datasets, integrated computing infrastructure and tools which demand less knowledge of AI from the user so that they can build innovative AI software. EOSC nodes have the potential of integrating their capabilities to provide access to advanced computing, datasets, models, software, training and user support to European researchers.

More and increasingly bigger scientific datasets are generated at research facilities and made available in 'data holdings' or 'FAIR data repositories'. Although datasets are offered as resources in these holdings for primary and secondary use – as the size of holdings, the size of individual datasets and the complexity of datasets grow – the re-use of data becomes practically impossible without technical knowledge of compute environments, data staging, data analysis and AI techniques.

While some of the data providers have been able to overcome this issue by offering pre-arranged compute capacities with cloud-hosted AI applications and user support for their users, there are still several RIs without such explicit 'exploitation environments', and the AI activities within some of the RI communities are rather sporadic – severely limiting the reuse and valorisation of their data from these holdings.

EOSC can provide the framework for establishing partnerships between data providers, AI services providers and e-infrastructure providers so that:

- RIs are responsible for managing data holdings replicas in the EGI federated cloud and for providing domain-specific data-intensive analysis tools. Data lifecycle management can benefit from coherent identity management, authentication and authorisation solutions that are available on EGI sites and ensure coherent trust controls and

³ https://apre.it/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/ec_rtd_ai-in-science-pb.pdf

⁴ https://erc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2023-12/AI_in_science.pdf

⁵

<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/2a6e3d4f-fae0-11ee-a251-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

interoperability across RIs, e-infrastructures and the emerging ecosystem of Data Spaces.

- The EGI Federation can host AI frameworks that can expose the replicated data to AI models for training/retraining on big scientific data for RI operators (for elevating data quality) and users (for data analysis).
- Dedicated EGI Federated clouds can offer an hosting environment for model servicing, where both foundation and trained AI models are shared, served and retrained including the emerging general-purpose AI solutions to accelerate the entire scientific research process—from the literature review and data analysis to scientific communication.

The contributions can establish a flourishing AI ecosystem that:

- Will significantly enhance the data analysis capacity of European research performing organisations, by providing scalable computational platforms and integrating AI frameworks. This will enable more complex, data-intensive research, accelerating scientific discoveries and technological innovations. The advancement of interoperable standards and protocols will also facilitate seamless data exchange and collaboration across different scientific domains, breaking down silos and enabling multidisciplinary research efforts.
- Will increase the technological level and AI capabilities of European RIs, and contribute to enhancing the scientific competitiveness of Europe on the global stage, attracting investments, and fostering economic growth.

With this approach EOSC can bring a foundational shift in how research is conducted, how RI data is analysed by enabling RIs to extend their services with scalable computational platforms suited for AI and other data-intensive application fields (e.g. digital twins), ensuring that European RIs remain at the forefront of global scientific research.

New AI-based services in the EGI portfolio for data use and reuse

Leveraging AI capabilities, EGI is working to extend its service portfolio to better support the research data lifecycle management with the development and provisioning of new services for the integrated discovery, analysis, deposition, sharing, use and reuse of research data.

AI-based natural language search tools, capable of integrating with heterogeneous sets of thematic, national and institutional repositories and other data sources, will be integrated in the EGI infrastructure to enable a common discovery channel for structured and unstructured multidisciplinary data. AI techniques will be also adopted to automatically couple data with processing and analytics tools, and execute them in a variety of software deployment

environments and processing platforms that are hosted in the EGI infrastructure. Results of the data analysis can be successively deposited in one of the repositories connected to the EGI infrastructure with sufficient metadata to enable their reuse and the reproducibility of science.

Thanks to these new AI-based services,, the EGI infrastructure plans to greatly facilitate data exploitation lowering the bar for researchers. EGI is intended to connect these new capabilities with several national, regional and thematic repositories to offer to its users a large amount of data spanning different scientific disciplines with the ultimate goal to foster multidisciplinary and remove barriers between research communities.

Furthermore, developments in EGI are also focusing towards providing researchers with an easy-to-use platform to manage general-purpose ML workflows, with limited engineering overhead, while providing state-of-the-art MLOps best practices. The platform, based on Kubeflow, instantiates ML workflows with the configurations provided by the developer over an Hybrid computing infrastructure, including Cloud, HTC and HPC providers. The execution of ML workflows produces as output a set of ML metrics, which are visualised via MLFlow. As a result of ML training, the best model (on validation dataset) is saved to a Models Registry for future predictions. Thanks to a Serverless framework integration, the platform can also easily scale AI inference activities and provide the researchers an integrated and seamless way to serve their trained models.

Concluding Remarks

We wish to conclude this discussion paper with the following remarks and recommendations.

1. Boost EOSC value proposition for data valorisation.

The EOSC Multi-Annual Roadmap and funding opportunities need to be aligned and focused on grand challenges that require the integration of research data, computing, storage, services and tools, knowledge and user support from multiple disciplines (i.e. above individual existing research infrastructures and e-Infrastructures).

EOSC has the potential to increase data valorisation for interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary data exploitation. This can be achieved by making available large datasets, tools and applications, AI/ML models and supporting compute facilities from EU Member States supporting research projects and collaborations that would otherwise not be possible due to policy, funding and technical constraints.

2. Increase adoption of AI/ML in research applications

European and national funding are needed to speed up the realisation of the vision of EOSC as a web of FAIR data and services providing AI-powered solutions that will support the researchers in all the phases of the data lifecycle and the scientific research process.

European and national funding are needed to speed up the realisation of the vision of EOSC as a web of FAIR data and services providing AI-powered solutions that will support the researchers in all the phases of the data lifecycle and the scientific research process.

These advanced services can facilitate the data discovery, the identification of appropriate tools to analyse such data and the data analysis, guiding the users on the selection of a processing platform and automating its deployment. e-Infrastructures and RIs need support to innovate with AI-based services (including general-purpose AI tools), removing policy and technical barriers to fully realise the research value chain of the wealth of research datasets, analysis platforms, and digital services of national and pan-European relevance currently available in the ERA.

3. EGI Federation as EOSC Node for data intensive computing and research data exploitation

The role of Computing and Storage is to enable the valorisation of research data in collaboration with data holders, promoting secondary cross-country and cross-institutional use and reuse of research objects.

The EGI Federation aspires to be part of the EOSC Federation as a Node contributing EOSC-dedicated distributed compute and storage capacity from its members, to support the exploitation of research objects and services in EOSC. EGI Federation is also committed to continuing its participation in the co-design, development and provisioning of the EOSC Core, in collaboration with research infrastructures, e-Infrastructures and other EOSC stakeholders.

4. On co-investment by the EU and Member States.

EU Commission funding should catalyse Member State funding, and contribute to activities that are sustained by national funding agencies expanding them. EGI supports a co-investment of the EU and Member States for the long-term sustainability of the EOSC, and in particular, focuses on the provision of the EOSC Research Objects, Services and Tools and Compute Storage Network and AAI supporting services.

Due to the federated nature of EOSC, multiple funding agencies will be involved with independent and complementary funding streams. Today's digital infrastructures for research

are primarily funded by national funding agencies focusing on the access needs of national research communities. Research Infrastructures and e-Infrastructures need sustainable mechanisms to finance the marginal costs incurred when supporting the secondary use of research objects, services and tools. In the short term, financial incentives need to be put in place to allow EOSC stakeholders to cooperate in implementing EOSC as a federation. In the medium term, new research financing rules need to be promoted which support and require opening digital infrastructures (or part of them) for secondary use.

5. EOSC and transnational access

Research Infrastructures and e-Infrastructures need EU support to continuously serve European research communities, and require stable EU instruments for long-term support cross-institute and cross-national access that overcome the current limitations experienced in short-lived projects.

To address grand challenges in a cross-national, cross-disciplinary science fashion at a European scale, Research Infrastructures and e-Infrastructures need to integrate their capabilities, cooperating in the delivery of complementary capabilities and aiming at simplifying today's fragmented access channels, and overcoming limitations imposed by current funding models.

Acknowledgements

This discussion paper gathers input from multiple experts, including EGI Executive Board and Council members, and external advisors.

EGI thanks all the contributors for their valuable input.